

"DeSci Live: Complex Systems Engineering for Cognitive Ecosystems using Active Inference" (6/21/2023)

Trusted Seed WEB3 + AI Unconference

Big picture

<2 hour participatory session

- First minutes —
 - Introductions and Context
 - Then we will start recording.
- Middle — Applying 🧠 [Active Entity Ontology for Science \(AEOS\)](#)
 - We'll work on this page (everyone will have edit access).
 - We will generate a [GNN](#) model of an [AEOS](#) Decentralized Science (DeSci) system.
- Last 30 minutes — Polish & Publish
 - After completing this page and [DeSci Live ~ Author](#) table, we will download as a PDF, then upload to [Zenodo](#) so all participants will be co-authors.
 - Then we will have an instant post-mortem analysis, in terms of how we could have done things better (seeing the situation as a DeSci microcosm) and where we'll go next.

Background and more information

- 📄 [Spinning up with Blockference & 🧩 Image Memes at 🏆 Active Blockference](#)
- Active Inference ([Textbook](#))
 - "First principles" framework for perception and action.
 - [Figure 1.1](#)
 - [Figure 2.3](#)
 - [Figure 3.1](#)
 - [Designing Ecosystems of Intelligence from First Principles, Friston et al. 2022](#)
 - [Designing explainable artificial intelligence with active inference: A framework for transparent introspection and decision-making \(2023\)](#)
- 🧠 [Active Entity Ontology for Science \(AEOS\)](#)
 - [An Active Inference Ontology for Decentralized Science: from Situated Sensemaking to the Epistemic Commons \(2022\)](#)

- All of the generalization/flexibility of the formalisms for @Action and @Perception is so that we can model different kinds of nested and interacting AEOS Entity Types.
 - For example a @Human talking to a @Computer System, within an @Team at an @Organizational Unit of a @Academic University or @DAO.
 - Different kinds of AEOS Entity Types have different capacities for @Perception and @Action
 - AEOS enables compositional modeling of cyberphysical systems.
- Generalized Notation Notation (GNN) —
 - Plaintext notation for Active Inference generative modeling.
 - This enables the “Triple Play” (natural language with Language Models, graphical visualizations, and executable cognitive system simulations with Active Blockference).
 - GNN specification: Source file structure, Punctuation, and Examples.
 - We will use GNN syntax to model a DeSci system of interest.

Cognitive modeling for DeSci

- We will do this together!
- Driving questions
 - What are we interested in modeling about DeSci ecosystems?
 - DeSci, DeSchool, DAOs, Hypercerts, etc.....
 - What is the minimum viable DeSci ecosystem?
 - How do we model Multiagent DeSci @Teams, @Organizations, and Ecosystems?
 - How do we balance Subject Matter Expertise (SME) with Prediction Matter Expertise (PME)?
 - What are some specific DeSci settings where a lot of agent-specific information is known?
 - What are the structural (macro) and the cognitive (micro, agentic) aspects of the situation?
 - How can we explore the intersection of Web3 and AI
 - How can we leverage the abilities of cadCAD in terms of cadCAD and Simulations?
 - Onboarding to TEC (@Community of Practice)
 - Can be hard without certain background features/knowledge
 - Familiarity with..... Web3, Blockchain, Language, Token engineer
 - Active entities
 - Human (roles: onboarding, community member, Steward)
 - Team
 - Bots
 - DAO
 - Commons
 - Information entities (static, files)
 - Forum

- Documentation
 - Case studies
 - Best practices
 - Webinars
 - Learning resources
 - Articles
- Below we will characterize a [🏠 DeSci GNN](#) . This will result in a Markdown file that describes the generative model of our system(s) of interest, and can be implemented according to the “Triple Play”.
 - sentiment analysis, adaptive learning platforms, virtual tutors, learning analytics, knowledge management, and support analytics to create a seamless learning experience that tailors learning pathways, tracks progress, and fosters knowledge sharing among community members
 - Onboarding of a person into the TEC.
 - Action
 - Visiting the website (or not)
 - Perception
 - Seeing the website (or not)

DeSci GNN

Synced from [here](#)

GNN Section	DeSci onboarding person.	Forum Website
Image from paper		
GNN version and flags		
Model name	Onboarding of a person into the TEC	
Model annotation	Towards sentiment analysis, adaptive learning platforms, virtual tutors, learning analytics, knowledge management, and support analytics to create a seamless learning experience that tailors learning pathways, tracks progress, and fosters knowledge sharing among community members	
State space block	Action[2,1] (visiting the website or not) Perception[2,1] (seeing the website or not) Can add more.	Action[2,1] — Serving the website or not Perception[2,1] — User request for website
Connections	Their action connects to Forum's sense. Their perception connects to Forum's action.	
Initial parameterization	Action[0.5,0.5] = They are equally likely to visit or not	
Equations		
Time		
ActInf Ontology annotation		
Footer		
Signature		

Publishing

Abstract

- This article was written in a session at the Trusted Seed's Web3 + AI Unconference on June 21, 2021.
- The discussion and model presented are not intended as anything but an initial exploration into what is possible with Decentralized Science (DeSci).
- We explored the Active Inference framework from a theoretical perspective, and how it is being applied in the area of Artificial Intelligence (AI).
- We then used the Active Entity Ontology for Science (AEOS) and Generalized Notation Notation (GNN) to make a simple model of a situation of interest: a person onboarding to the Token Engineering Commons (TEC).
- Future work could:
 - Expand on the current model to more comprehensively describe the onboarding process.
 - Explore what other situations might be modeled with a similar approach.

- Consider how the values and norms of a Commons are enacted in design and operation.

DeSci Live ~ Author

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Feedback & Reflection

- Learnings
 - ...
- Questions
 - ...
- Next steps
 - ...
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